

[Vasco Nunes MSc.] Large Language Models in Low-Code and Model-Driven Platforms: A Systematic Literature Review

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This systematic literature review analyses how Large Language Models are applied in low-code and model-driven platforms. It identifies current methods, representations, and challenges related to the automatic generation of structured artefacts such as rules, workflows, and models.

Planning

The goal of this systematic literature review is to identify, classify, and analyse approaches that integrate Large Language Models (LLMs) into low-code and model-driven environments. The review aims to understand the methods, intermediate representations, and validation techniques used to generate structured artefacts automatically.

PICOC

- **Population:** Studies, frameworks, and platforms related to low-code and model-driven development.
- **Intervention:** The use of Large Language Models to generate, assist, or validate structured artefacts such as rules, workflows, or models.
- **Comparison:** Traditional rule/model generation methods without AI assistance, or non-LLM approaches.
- **Outcome:** Identified methods, intermediate representations, validation techniques, and challenges in integrating LLMs with low-code platforms.
- **Context:** Low-code and model-driven development environments, practical application within the DISME platform.

Research Questions

1. How are Large Language Models (LLMs) integrated into low-code and model-driven platforms?
2. What types of intermediate or structured representations are used between natural language inputs and executable artefacts?
3. What mechanisms ensure syntactic and semantic correctness of LLM-generated artefacts?
4. How are these approaches evaluated, and what benefits or limitations are reported in AI-assisted low-code development?

Keywords and Synonyms

Keyword	Synonyms
Intermediate Representation	DSL, JSON, XML, grammar-based format, structured representation
Large Language Models	ChatGPT, GPT, LLM, generative AI, transformer-based models
Low-Code Platforms	business process platforms, model-based development, no-code, visual programming
Model-Driven Development	MDD, MDE, domain-specific modelling, model-driven engineering
Rule Generation	model generation, process automation, rule synthesis, workflow modelling
Validation and Verification	grammar checking, schema validation, semantic validation, syntax checking

Search String

("low-code" OR "no-code" OR "model-driven" OR "model-driven development" OR "model-driven engineering" OR "MDD" OR "MDE" OR "model-based development" OR "business process platforms" OR "visual programming" OR "domain-specific modelling")

AND

("large language model" OR "LLM" OR "GPT" OR "ChatGPT" OR "generative AI" OR "transformer" OR "transformer-based model")

AND

("intermediate representation" OR "structured representation" OR "domain-specific language" OR "DSL" OR "JSON" OR "XML" OR "grammar-based format")

AND

("rule generation" OR "workflow generation" OR "model generation" OR "process automation" OR "rule synthesis" OR "workflow modelling" OR "validation" OR "verification" OR "schema validation" OR "semantic validation" OR "syntax checking" OR "grammar checking")

Sources

- ACM Digital Library (<http://portal.acm.org>)
- IEEE Digital Library (<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org>)
- Science@Direct (<http://www.sciencedirect.com>)

- Scopus (<http://www.scopus.com>)
- Springer Link (<http://link.springer.com>)

Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- The paper discusses or applies Large Language Models (LLMs) or transformer-based models.
- The paper must be written in English.
- The paper must have been published between 2020 and 2025.
- The study is peer-reviewed and presents original research (journal or conference paper).

Exclusion Criteria:

- Papers not peer-reviewed (e.g., blogs, posters, editorials, tutorials).
- Papers with fewer than 6 pages or insufficient technical detail.
- Papers written in languages other than English.

Quality Assessment Checklist

Questions:

- Were the research goals and questions clearly stated?
- Was the research design or experimental setup clearly described?
- Was related work adequately reviewed and compared with claimed results?
- Does the study explicitly involve Large Language Models (LLMs) or transformer-based methods?
- Does the paper address low-code, no-code, or model-driven platforms, tools, or workflows?
- Does the study define or use structured or intermediate representations?
- Were validation or evaluation methods (quantitative or qualitative) clearly reported and appropriate?
- Are the results credible, reproducible, and supported by sufficient evidence?

Answers:

- Yes
- Partially

- No

Data Extraction Form

- Title
- Authors / Year
- Source / Venue
- Type of Study
- License / Accessibility
- Platform Type
- Platform Licensing
- LLM/Model Used
- Other Models Used/Mentioned
- Model Access Type
- Uses Intermediate Representation (IR)?
- IR Type
- IR Specification Method
- IR Language Category
- Purpose of Representation
- Syntax Enforcement Mechanism
- Persistence Format
- Output Type
- Human-in-the-loop Level
- Executable Artefact Generated
- Evaluation Method
- Validation Type
- Sample Size/ N Participants
- Main Findings
- Reported Challenges/ Limitations

Conducting

Digital Libraries Search Strings

Imported Studies

- **ACM Digital Library:** 33
- **IEEE Digital Library:** 17
- **Science@Direct:** 14
- **Springer Link:** 5